

Health Monitoring and Fall Detection System for Elderly

(Sistem Pemantauan Kesihatan dan Pengesanan Kejatuhan untuk Warga Tua)

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ABSTRACT

Health and safety issues are very important for human beings in addition to health disease which are the number one cause of death in Malaysia as stated by Official Portal of the Ministry of Health Malaysia. Besides, the falls problem for the elderly is a big issue compared to young people, the problem of falls is a small incident but a no for seniors who have other subsequent relationships for chronic diseases such as osteoporosis which is high risk for fractures and difficult to recover from the falling incidents. This document proposes a combination of two systems which are health monitoring system and fall detection system based on the kinematic method that aims to aid elderly to constantly monitor their health condition and seek for assistance when they fell. It has two main part which are health monitoring system using pulse oximeter MAX30102 sensor and fall detection system using the IMU accelerometer and gyroscope of MPU-9250 sensor. In health monitoring system, there are three parameters measured which are heart rate (BPM), oxygen level (SPO2) and body temperature. The health information will be stored in BLYNK cloud for analysis process and will be displayed on the high contrast OLED screen display. While in fall detection system part, the MPU-9250 sensor analyses the acceleration and angular velocity of the user's hand then alerting people nearby or emergency contact if the falling condition is detected. All continuous count of acceleration magnitude (AM) data will be taken and is calculated to be compared with the threshold set to indicate the falling condition. This study uses the Database and Online Analysis (BLYNK) technology as the data storage cloud, Wireless Interface Communication (IFTTT) application and buzzer as the emergency alert, and NodeMCU ESP32 as microcontroller.

Keywords: Health monitoring; Fall detection; Accelerometer and gyroscope; Pulse oximeter

ABSTRAK

Isu-isu berkaitan kesihatan dan keselamatan diri adalah sangat penting bagi manusia tambahan lagi penyakit jantung adalah penyebab kematian nombor satu di Malaysia seperti yang dinyatakan oleh Portal Rasmi Kementerian Kesihatan Malaysia. Selain itu, masalah kejatuhan bagi warga tua adalah isu besar berbanding warga muda, masalah kejatuhan adalah insiden kecil tetapi tidak bagi warga tua yang kurang ketahanan seterusnya membawa kepada penyakit kronik seperti osteoporosis yang berisiko tinggi untuk tulang mudah patah dan sukar pulih daripada insiden jatuh. Dokumen ini mencadangkan gabungan dua sistem iaitu sistem pemantauan kesihatan dan sistem pengesanan kejatuhan berasaskan kaedah kinematik untuk membantu warga tua memantau keadaan kesihatan dan mengesan kejatuhan secara berterusan. Kajian ini mempunyai dua bahagian iaitu sistem pemantauan kesihatan menggunakan penderia nadi oksimeter MAX30102 dan sistem pengesanan kejatuhan dari penderia meter pecut dan giroskop IMU (unit pengukuran inersia) MPU-9250. Dalam sistem pemantauan kesihatan, terdapat tiga parameter yang diukur iaitu kadar denyutan jantung (BPM), tahap oksigen (SPO2) dan suhu badan. Setrusnya, informasi kesihatan itu akan disimpan dalam penyimpanan data aplikasi BLYNK untuk dianalisis dan dipaparkan pada paparan skrin OLED berkontras tinggi. Manakala bagi sistem pengesanan kejatuhan, penderia MPU-9250 akan menganalisa pecutan dan halaju sudut tangan pengguna, seterusnya memberi amaran kepada orang sekeliling atau kenalan kecemasan sekiranya keadaan jatuh dikesan. Semua data mentah magnitud pecutan (AM) yang diambil secara berterusan akan dianalisis dan dibandingkan dengan nilai ambang yang ditetapkan bagi mengesan keadaan jatuh. Kajian ini menggunakan teknologi Pangkalan Data dan Analisis Dalam Talian (BLYNK) sebagai aplikasi penyimpanan data, aplikasi Komunikasi Pengantaramukaan Tanpa Wayar (IFTTT) serta penggera sebagai amaran kecemasan, dan NodeMCU ESP32 sebagai mikropengawal.

Kata Kunci: Pemantauan kesihatan; Pengesanan kejatuhan; Meter pecut dan giroskop; Oksimeter nadi

INTRODUCTION

Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) technology with smart sensor nodes is a significant proof of identification technology for a wide range of applications. Using the WSN concept, a study on health monitoring and fall tracking systems was conducted. The main purpose of the study is to help the public especially the elderly to monitor their health and get help when falling using NodeMCU ESP32 technology from Arduino to the Database and Online Analysis (BLYNK) mobile application and Wireless Interface Communication (IFTTT) web application. Health and safety issues are very important for human beings in addition to health disease which are the number one cause of death in Malaysia as stated by the Deputy Minister of Health (Yusof, 2019). Besides, the falls problem for the elderly is a big issue compared to young people, the problem of falls is a small incident but a no for seniors who have other subsequent relationships for chronic diseases such as osteoporosis which is high risk for fractures and difficult to recover from the falling incidents (Dionyssiotis, 2012). Therefore, the health and wellness system has been designed to focus on the issue of elderly care to prevent serious accidents from occurring and they managed to get help immediately.

The literature review is divided into two main parts which are the health monitoring system and the fall detection system so that the methods used are more clearly described. The health monitoring system highlights measured parameters such as heart rate, body temperature and oxygen levels using the appropriate sensors. All parameters are measured and processed using a microcontroller and a warning will be sent when it exceeds the set threshold value.

The following are some of the library studies used as a reference in this project for the health monitoring system. The results of the study (Jubadi & Sahak, 2009), using photoplethysmography (PPG) technique to detect heart rate. This signal is processed using the PIC16F87 microcontroller to determine the heart rate per minute. Then, a warning is sent via Short Message Service (SMS) to the mobile phone of the physician or family member of the patient, or relatives. The heartbeat sensor circuit using PPG technique is designed using MAPLAB software. In (Gopi et al. 2016) also explains the concept of single chip microcontroller can be used to analyze heart rate in real time. In addition, the system allows doctors to obtain heart rate and patient location using Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM) technology at all times in addition to controlling patients for long periods of time. The system reads the stored data and analyzes the data (heart rate) repeatedly in real time.

While the second part of this project is the fall detection system. The issue of falls is one of the most

common health problems faced by the elderly. The consequences of a fall can be fatal if there is no immediate medical treatment. A reliable and cost-effective smart fall detection system must be considered as an option to help the elderly. Existing techniques used to design a fall detection system are classified into three categories namely camera-based methods, acoustic-based methods and kinematic-based methods. The following are among the library studies divided into the following three categories that are used as a reference for this system.

Firstly, the camera-based fall detection system method uses several sets of cameras and a microcontroller or personal computer (PC) as a dedicated server. Generally, cameras are used to capture video or images and then transfer them to a PC to analyze and process images, reaching people from the background and detecting falling conditions. In the study (Yu et al. 2012), global (elliptical) and local (shape context) properties of static postures and the improved Directed Acyclic Graphic Support Vector Machine (DAGSVM) were used to classify postures. Once the posture is classified into several different parts such as lying or bending, limbs in the ground area, both posture conditions exceed 30 seconds, certain rules will be set to detect falls.

Secondly for the fall detection using acoustic-based method, the acoustic and ambient sensors are used to detect falls among the elderly. The cost for this method is relatively cheap compared to the camera-based method due to the low cost of hardware and implementation. Examples of acoustic sensors and environments used are infrared sensors, vibration sensors and microphones. These sensors will collect the data and then transfer it to a microcontroller for processing. Fall detection is only activated when the collected data exceeds certain thresholds or conditions set by the microcontroller. (Li et al. 2012) proposed an acoustic fall detection system (acoustic-FADE) consisting of a set of round microphones that capture sound in a room. This system results from the problem of the effect of lying on the floor for a long time due to falling. When sound is detected, acoustics-FADE finds its source, enhances the signal, and classifies it as "falling" or "not falling".

Finally, for kinematic-based fall detection systems, accelerometer and gyroscope are placed on the user's body parts to distinguish falling conditions from daily life activities (ADL). The data collected by the sprint meter and gyroscope are sent to the microcontroller for processing. Since this method is a wearable device, the operating range is not a major problem. (Siregar et al. 2018) in their study using the Arduino Uno as a microcontroller, accelerometer sensor and gyroscope that serves to measure the falling motion of the elderly and is supported by Ublox Neo 6M GPS technology to provide

information on coordinates. However, it is quite expensive.

This paper aims to implement a health monitoring system that monitors heart rate (BPM), oxygen levels (SPO2) and body temperature as well as a fall detection system based on kinematic methods that are cost effective and affordable.

METHODOLOGY

FIGURE 1. Steps taken in the development of the health monitoring and fall detection system

Research of Health Monitoring and Fall Detection System

Several studies have been conducted to find out the current health monitoring and fall detection systems and identify problems that arise while using them. Most systems nowadays like the Apple Watch Series 5 GPS that have GPS and key feature for fall detection are expensive and complicated (Senheng, 2020). In addition, the systems used in the past used microcontrollers and technologies that are somewhat outdated for use today. Therefore, this study was conducted as an initiative to detect the fall while simultaneously monitoring health using hardware and software with an affordable budget and the latest technology (Harun et al. 2011; Mahmood et al. 2011).

System Design

The main part of this system design is to combine the health monitoring system and fall detection system and using Database and Online Analysis (BLYNK) technology as well as Wireless Interface Communication (IFTTT) application and NodeMCU ESP32 as microcontroller. Figure 2 shows the schematic circuit diagram of the system.

FIGURE 2. Schematic circuit diagram

Research methods and measures carried out in the development of health monitoring and fall detection system in terms of hardware, software and testing are detailed based on Figure 1. At the beginning of the study, the research methodology and strategies used to obtain information and data to start the study were planned in an orderly manner. The research methodology aims to help understand in more detail the application of the method by making a description of the research process.

The hardware involved are NodeMCU ESP32 as microcontroller, MAX30102 Pulse Oximeter and MPU9250 sensors as input, and also OLED Display and buzzer as output. MAX30102 is an integrated pulse oximetry and heart-rate monitor biosensor module (Longmore et al., 2019) used for health monitoring system. While MPU9250 sensor a Nine-Axis (Gyrometer + Accelerometer + Compass) MEMS Motion Tracking Device. The MPU-9250 is a System in Package (SiP) that combines two chips: the MPU-6500, which contains a 3-axis gyroscope, a 3-axis accelerometer and a 3-axis digital compass (TDK InveSense -, 2017). This sensor used for the motion tracking in fall detection method.

Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) software is used in this project because Arduino Uno can be programmed in accordance with the purpose of the system implemented. Arduino IDE software for writing, compiling and even adding program code to the Arduino Uno microcontroller. In addition, MATLAB software is also used in this project to analyze acceleration data and angular velocity. Next, the IFTTT application which is one of the Wireless Interface Communication applications is also used for the use of alert notifications to the emergency contact of the data time for the set value drop system. IFTTT asks for each programming conditional statement "if this, then that" which is a free web-provided service for creating a network of simple conditional statements, used as an applet (James A. Martin, 2019). In short, IFTTT is a software platform that helps all applications, devices and services from different development to trigger one or more automations that use those applications, devices and services. The system uses BLYNK software for NOdeMCU ESP32 modification as an online database and analysis.

This study requires testing of the Arduino microcontroller and each hardware such as sensors to take input data before design development is done to ensure there are no problems in prototype testing and data analysis. The system starts with the continuous collection of raw data from all sensors using the Pulse Oximeter MAX30102 sensor and MPU9250 sensor. Next, the data taken is processed and divided into two part which are continuous calculation of acceleration magnitude (AM) using MATLAB for the fall detection system and for health monitoring parameters i.e. heart rate, body temperature and oxygen resistance (SPO2) will be measured, displayed on high contrast OLED display screen as information observation consumer health. For the continuous calculation of acceleration magnitude (AM), the data that has been taken and calculated will be compared with the threshold set using MATLAB software. If the threshold value is set, an alarm sound to warn people around will be sounded and short message signal (SMS) will be received by emergency contacts using Database and Online Analysis (BLYNK) technology and Wireless Interface Communication (IFTTT) application.

The system begins by constantly collecting raw data from both sensors, the pulse oximeter and the motion tracking sensor (accelerometer and gyroscope), for detecting vital signs of the user (which are heartbeat per minute, body temperature, and oxygen concentration), and real-time motion of the user, respectively. The data from both sensors are processed by the microcontroller. The health data collected from the pulse oximeter is sent to the OLED screen for displaying at the smart wearable device and is also sent to BLYNK through Wi-Fi for real-time health monitoring through mobile application. In the meanwhile, the system will constantly collect the user's motion data from the sensor. If the acceleration magnitude exceeded the threshold value and the angular velocity remains constant for a small period of time, the system will assume a fall and will triggered the buzzer to alert the people nearby and will also send a notification to alert the present emergency contact when the user experiences a fall. Figure 3 shows the flow chart of the health monitoring and fall detection system.

FIGURE 3. Flow chart for health monitoring and fall detection system

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Display for Health Monitoring System

The device power supply and Wi-Fi connection are turned on to start communication between online applications and hardware. The user's wrist or finger should be in contact with the light emitted by the MAX30102. Figure 4 shows the data displayed on the OLED screen after the user's finger is in contact with the MAX30102 sensor.

FIGURE 4. The data displayed on OLED screen

Table 1 shows the threshold values of the display on the OLED screen which shows data on heart rate per minute (BPM), body temperature and oxygen level (SPO2).

TABLE 1. The threshold values for health monitoring.

Normal Condition	
Heart Rate (BPM)	60-100
Body Temperature	37 °C
Oxygen Level (SPO2)	<95%

Next, the health monitoring data will constantly be uploaded from NodeMCU ESP32 to BLYNK to apply online, via Wi-Fi in real time. Users will be able to monitor the state of health through graphical analysis visible from the BLYNK application. Additionally, historical data can be stored in the cloud and can be sent in .csv file type, for further analysis by a physician. The creation of a project that displays BPM and SPO2 readings on the phone application and changes before and after the code is uploaded on the gauge and displayed parameters.

Analysis and Result of Fall Detection System

After the power supply device is turned on, the MPU-9250 will run continuously to detect acceleration and velocity of the user. The preset threshold value for acceleration is 2 meters per square second while the preset threshold value for

angular velocity is 200 degrees per second. If the value detected by the sensor exceeds both threshold values at the same time, this indicates a fall detection by the system, and the device will continue to detect the user angle after falling for a period of 5 seconds. Once the orientation does not change in 50 degrees per second (dps), the system will assume that the user is unconscious after falling. Then, the microcontroller will write a 'HIGH' level of logic to the pin set to activate the alarm and send a warning message to the account registered through the IFTTT web application. The most commonly used threshold analysis with acceleration data is the total acceleration of vector magnitude, which reflects the level of body activity, given by Equation (1), where ax, ay, and az are accelerations in the directions of x, y and z.

$$asqrt = \sqrt{ax^2 + ay^2 + az^2} \tag{1}$$

Similarly, the threshold used with gyroscope data is the sum of the vectors of the magnitude of the angular velocity and is calculated from the sample data as expressed in the following Equation (2), where wx, wy, and wz are angular velocity in the directions x, y and z.

$$wsqrt = \sqrt{wx^2 + wy^2 + wz^2} \tag{2}$$

Figure 5 shows the analysis of the study of acceleration by the accelerometer and gyroscope for angular velocity by the state to trigger the collapse. Several studies were conducted for reference and improvement, and the results of these experiments were recorded and displayed.

FIGURE 5. Acceleration analysis and angular velocity when falling conditions are triggered

CONCLUSION

The results of the study stated that the objectives of the study were almost achieved with the result of a health monitoring system and fall detection. Live data for health monitoring was successfully transmitted via the NodeMCU ESP-32 WiFi module from the Arduino to the BLYNK mobile application. However, due to time constraints and hardware and software problems during the study, the use of IFTTT as an immediate notification to the emergency line when in a dangerous situation was not successful. In addition, the sensitivity and accuracy limitations of the sensors' data used are unsatisfactory.

There are suggestions for improvement to overcome limitations and improve the findings of the study. The most significant improvement that can be made is the improvement in terms of accuracy and sensitivity of the sensors used in the study. The values of sensitivity and accuracy of health monitoring systems and fall detection can be achieved with a fully satisfactory level if the improvement of the current algorithm to produce the optimal output is performed.

In addition, the results of the study of the health monitoring system are limited to the reading of BPM, SPO2 and body temperature due to the estimated budget and limited implementation time of the study for the entire project. This can be overcome by requesting sponsorship from certain parties for the addition of other external features such as blood pressure, ECG, EGG and blood glucose readings that can be added in the health monitoring system to detect diseases that may be faced by the elderly.

Finally, global positioning systems (GPS) and global systems for mobile communications (GSM) could not be implemented due to time constraints from the study design period as well as hardware problems. Switching the system wireless connection to a GSM or LTE module so that the wearable system device can be used for external purposes without being attached to the Wi-Fi module is one of the thoughtful suggestions for future improvement.

In conclusion, although there are limitations in the study produced, this study has proven that kinematic-based distance detection using MPU-9250 sensor and health display for low-cost monitoring has been successfully produced. This study is expected to help the problem of the elderly who need monitoring of those around them as well as provide a good platform for the learning environment and get experience workspace.

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